

STRATEGY FOR DEVELOPING MUSEUM MANAGEMENT TO PROMOTE LEARNING FOR THE PEOPLE OF THE UPPER NORTHEASTERN REGION 1

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ABSTRACT

The objectives of this research were to 1) study the problems of museum management in promoting learning among people in the Upper Northeastern Region1, 2) Formulate strategy for Developing Museum Management to Promote Learning for The People of The Upper Northeastern Region 1. This developmental research is divided into 2 phases. Phase 1 studies the problem of museum management in promoting learning among people in the Upper Northeastern Region1, Uses research The target group was 9 experts, and the sample group was determined to be 111 people, research tools include semi-structured interviews and questionnaires, analyzing the content data and using statistics, frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation phase 2 to create a strategy for Developing Museum Management to Promote Learning for The People of The Upper Northeastern Region 1. Target groups include 15 experts and 30 experts, confirming the development strategy's suitability and feasibility. The research tools were suitability and feasibility assessment forms. To analyze data using statistics, frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Research results. the problem of museum management problems in promoting public learning in the upper northeastern region.

When classified by each aspect, they included planning, organizing, reporting, budgeting, coordination, personnel management, and supervision and the strategic frameworks for enhancing museum management consist of guiding principles, objectives, initiatives, and performance indicators. The four core strategies ware: 1) Developing personnel to ensure effective planning; 2) Improving organizational management; 3) Enhancing reporting accuracy; and 4) Increasing efficiency in budget management. The evaluation of these strategies indicates that Strategy 2, related to organizational management, demonstrates the highest feasibility and appropriateness. the results after undertaking a confirmation strategy suggested that both overall value higher than 3.51 which is considered acceptable based on the assessment criteria that have been established.

Keywords: Strategies Developing, Museum Management, Promote Learning, The Upper Northeastern Region 1

Cite this Article: Kritsada Chaopron, Bussagorn Suksan and Krittikar Sanposh. (2024). Strategy for Developing Museum Management to Promote Learning for the People of The Upper Northeastern Region 1. *International Journal of Management*, 15(6), 109–119. https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJM/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_6/IJM_15_06_009.pdf

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of museums is considered an extension of knowledge from the unique identity of the province that can convey stories in the past through the process of storytelling, creating awareness, creating valuable knowledge, and also increasing service options for the tourism industry in the form of quality tourist attractions created with historical and cultural capital of the locality that can create attraction for tourists who are interested in visiting and opening new experiences in areas that are important in terms of history and culture, as well as being a valuable source of learning about stories in the past that can create impressions and learning experiences in the future. Upper Northeast 1 There are museums divided by management type in 5 provinces in the Upper Northeast 1, namely 1) Foundations and non-profit organizations 2) Educational institutions 3) Temples 4) Communities 5) Government agencies 6) National museums 7) Business organizations 8) Individuals and 9) Local administrative organizations, consisting of Udon Thani Province with 12 locations, Loei Province with 15 locations, Nong Bua Lamphu Province with 2 locations, Nong Khai Province with 7 locations, and Bueng Kan Province with 1 location, totaling 37 locations (Sirindhorn Anthropology Centre , 2024) If the museum is developed, it will become an important learning resource (Predee Pleumsamrankit and Fa Wilai Kham , 2018).

According to the research report of Museum: Learning Source for Developing Learners in the 21st Century, it is stated that museums are valuable learning sources and create a learning society. They help stimulate learning, both in knowing oneself and others, and train learners to have thinking skills which are important skills for living in the 21st century. Museums in the 21st century will be a source of lifelong learning, provide academic information, link academics with a good quality of life in society, and are also a tourist attraction for all people. Therefore, museums in Thailand should develop various aspects to be a learning source for learners in the 21st century, including places for exhibitions and activity promotion, space management, cooperation, public relations, and personnel. This article presents the meaning, importance, types of museums, and museums as a learning source for developing learners in the 21st century.

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It also discusses the problems of local museums, including problems of administrative structure, budget management , activity plans , problems of participation in the development of local curricula, activity leaders , participation , museum networks , researching local history, problems of presenting information , personnel development , exhibitions , services for resting areas , knowledge of services, and public relations. It also proposes guidelines for the management of local museums. The management of local museums to promote lifelong learning by organizing a seminar forum for 4 museums found that the management approach is balanced in 4 dimensions: Dimension 1: management of structure and plans; Dimension 2: management of participation; Dimension 3: management of resources to promote learning (Phisit Nat Prasert , Kampanat Boriboon , and Sumalee Sangsri , 2017).

From the above, the researcher sees the importance of conducting research on the strategy for developing museum management to promote learning of the people in the upper northeastern region 1 to study the problems of museum management to promote learning of the people in the upper northeastern region 1. Then, the obtained data will be used to develop a strategy for developing museum management to promote learning of the people in the upper northeastern region 1 and conduct experiments and evaluate the strategy for developing museum management to promote learning of the people in the upper northeastern region 1 before actually applying it. The obtained data can be further applied by relevant agencies.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THIS STUDY

To study the problems of museum management in promoting learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1.

To create the strategy for developing museum management to promote learning for people in the upper northeastern region 1.

III. DELIMITATION OF THIS STUDY

The key informants are experts of museum management in promoting learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1. Data collection method for qualitative research of 9 experts and the sample group was determined to be 111 people and distributed questionnaires and create the strategy for developing museum management to promote learning for people in the upper northeastern region 1. Target groups include 15 experts the museum's management team, key staff, as well as stakeholders and 30 experts, confirming the development strategy's suitability and feasibility.

IV. METHOD IN THIS STUDY

It is a mixed research method using both qualitative and quantitative research methods carried out in 2 phases as follows:

Phase 1 research studies of problems in museum management in promoting learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1 is a variety of research (Mix Method Research). There are 2 steps as follows:

Step 1 study the problem in museum management in promoting learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1. Qualitative research The target group is 9 museum managers. The research instrument used was a semi-structured interview. The data obtained from the interviews were analyzed using content analysis and overall summary.

Step 2 the problem in museum management in promoting learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1. conducting quantitative research population Including the administrators of 37 local museums, secretaries, and treasurers, 3 people per museum, totaling 111 people by selecting the entire population. The tool used in the research was a questionnaire. 2 episodes as follows: Part 1: General information of the respondents. Part 2 : Questionnaire to study the level of museum management problems in promoting learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1 The instrument is a 5-level Likert - type rating scale for measuring the level of opinion, with the following scoring criteria. Research tools: the researcher used a questionnaire created by the researcher himself by using data from literature studies that document concepts and theories; It is a 5-level estimation, divided into 3 parts, part 1 asks for basic information about the respondents. It is a checklist by asking about gender, age, education level, part 2 asked about the the problem in museum management in promoting learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1. It is a 5-level rating scale according to the Likert Method (Boonchom Srisaard, 2010) as follows:

- 5 represents the highest level of problem.
- 4 means a high level of problem
- 3 means the level of problem is moderate.
- 2 means less problem level.
- 1 represents the lowest level of problem.

Statistics based on data analysis are the percentage, mean, and standard deviation in the discussion of results; to describe the results obtained from a scale questionnaire. Estimated values considering the average score level according to 5 criteria (Boonchom Srisaat, 2010). A questionnaire was drafted and used as a research tool. The revised tool was then brought to the experts to check content validity and the language used (wording) and finally, scores from all 15 experts were taken to find the correspondence index between the items of each question with the purpose to be measured (Index of Item – Objective Congruence: IOC). This was achieved by using the formula of Rovinelli and Hambleton referred to in Boonchom Srisaat, (2010). The questionnaire's IOC value was 0.67-1.00. The questions were considered consistent with the content. The modified tool was later tested with a sample of 30 people to find the alpha coefficient (Alpha-coefficient) of the whole questionnaire using Cronbach's method (1970) (Cronbach), a value was 0.86. The method of data collection - The researcher distributed questionnaires, collected the data, and verified the completeness of the data in the questionnaire manually along with the questionnaire to interpret the results is the code according to the manual by entering the prepared code, saving, and processing. The data analysis obtained from closed-ended questionnaires and used as statistics mean analysis which was applied from Boonchom Srisaard (2010) as follows:

- Mean value between 4.51–5.00 means the highest level.
- Mean value between 3.51–4.50 means a high level.
- Mean value between 2.51–3.50 means moderate.
- Mean value between 1.51-2.50 means low level
- Mean value between 1.00-1.50 means the lowest level.

Statistics based on data analysis are the percentage (Percentage), mean (Mean), and Standard Deviation (Standard Division: S.D.) in the discussion of results; (Class Interval) to describe the results obtained from a scale questionnaire. Estimated values considering the average score level according to 5 criteria (Boonchom Srisaat, 2010).

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Phase 2: To create the strategy for developing museum management to promote learning for people in the upper northeastern region 1. The research is divided into 2 steps as follows:

Step 1: Create the draft strategy for developing museum management to promote learning for people in the upper northeastern region 1, The researcher used the results of the first phase study as a framework for analyzing the internal and external environments, using the SWOT technique. The target group was experts with knowledge and experience in developing museum management to promote learning for people in the upper northeastern region 1, totaling 15 people, selected purposively. By the workshop, analyzing data, content analysis (Content Analysis) and summarizing the overall .

Step 2: Evaluation of the strategy for developing museum management to promote learning for people in the upper northeastern region 1 The researcher evaluated the appropriateness and feasibility of the draft strategy for developing museum management to promote learning for people in the upper northeastern region 1 target group. consisting of 30 qualified persons involved in museum development in government agencies, including local museum administrators, leaders of cultural organizations, local community leaders, and experts in charge of museum management, selected specifically. The research instrument is an assessment form for the appropriateness and feasibility of the draft strategy for developing museum management to promote learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1. The scoring criteria were set in the form of a rating scale using the Liker Method by purposive selection, totaling 30 people, choosing a specific method (Purposive Sampling), Research instruments The researcher used an assessment form to assess the suitability, and feasibility of the strategy as a scale to perform scoring according to the criteria that determined the scores of the 5 weight ranges as follows:

5 means the assessment is at the highest level

4 means the assessment is at a high level

3 means the assessment is at a moderate level

2 means the assessment is at a low level

1 means the lowest rating

Data Collection 1) The researcher coordinated with the sample group to inform the objectives and benefits of the research and requested permission to collect data; 2) The researcher collected the data by calling the appointment in advance and then taking the assessment together with a request for cooperation; and 3) The researcher traveled to collect data by himself. Data analysis by content analysis and synthesis content then a descriptive overview was summarized and data analysis the researcher analyzed the data by using a ready-made program that analyzed frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The results were interpreted according to the following analytical criteria (Boonchom Srisaat, 2010).

Mean value between 4.51-5.00 suitability and feasibility is at the highest level.

Mean value between 3.51-4.50 suitability and feasibility is at a high level.

Mean value between 2.51-3.50 suitability and feasibility is at a moderate level.

Mean value between 1.51-2.50 suitability and feasibility is at a low level.

Mean value between 1.00-1.50 suitability and feasibility is at the lowest level.

The researcher has set the criteria that for the assessment to pass, the assessment must have a means of no less than 3.51 to be considered the evaluation is passed criteria.

V. CONCLUSION

From the research on strategy for developing museum management to promote learning for people in the upper northeastern region 1. The results of the research were summarized as follows:

Phase 1 The Problems in museum management in promoting learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1

1. The qualitative research results by interviewing 9 people. Found that 1) Most of it was found that the majority were male (77.79%), aged between 45 and 54 years (88.89 %), had a master's degree (66.67 %), and were married (77.78 %), 2) Results of interviews with experts and Found that Problems, core competencies Including Competency 1: focusing on results in work, including, In terms of planning, there are the following problems: 1) Insufficient or unreliable information. Planning that lacks information or unreliable information may prevent decision-making from being as expected. 2) Lack of clarity in the goals and details of the plan and details of the plan may prevent appropriate implementation of the plan. 3) Limitations in resources. Limitations in resources such as capital, personnel, or space may prevent the plan from being fully implemented. 4) Changes in external conditions may prevent the plan from being implemented.

Organizational issues include: 1) Segregation of important tasks or lack of clear assignment of duties, which leads to delays in implementation. 2) Creating an inappropriate organizational culture that supports learning and development. If there is a disconnect between the culture and the goals of the museum, the organization may have difficulty promoting learning effectively. 3) Unclear requirements and policies for operations. The absence of systematic guidance and instructions may lead to confusion and confusion in implementation. 4) Creating organizational energy. Museum management may have difficulty creating organizational energy that supports learning and development in the long run. Developing personnel and creating understanding about the museum can be a challenge.

In terms of human resource management, the problems are as follows: 1) Lack of skilled labor. Finding and retaining personnel who are capable and skilled in promoting learning can be challenging. In addition, promoting the development of skills and knowledge of existing personnel to enable them to perform their jobs effectively is an important factor. 2) Managing personnel efficiency: Promoting work efficiency and developing personnel's skills can be a challenge, for example, feedback and support for development may be insufficiently diverse and inclusive. 3) Creating an organizational culture that supports learning: An organizational culture that does not support learning can be a major obstacle affecting personnel development and the promotion of learning in museums. 4) Limitations in supporting personal development: Sometimes personnel may lack support for personal development and further education, for example, budget constraints or time available for further education.

In terms of administration, the problems are as follows: 1) Limitations in access and service provision Museums may face difficulties in facilitating access and service provision to visitors. There may be limitations in resources in terms of space, personnel or technology that can affect the visitor experience. 2) Creating facilities for visitors with special needs Having appropriate facilities for visitors with special needs, such as the disabled or the elderly, can be a management challenge. 3) Dealing with cultural and linguistic diversity Serving culturally and linguistically diverse visitor groups may require specific facilities to ensure that everyone has appropriate access and understanding of information. 4) Display management Inadequate facilities for display management and communication of information in a museum can affect visitors' understanding and learning experiences.

Coordination problems include : 1) Lack of communication between departments or units Lack of communication between departments or units within the museum can lead to incomplete information and operational guidelines. This can be an obstacle to creating a fully enriching learning experience. 2) Unclear messages about operating procedures Unclear messages about operating procedures or responsibilities between departments can lead to confusion and operational errors.

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3) Lack of coordination between projects or activities Lack of coordination between related projects or activities in the museum can lead to duplication or lack of organization in promoting learning. 4) Limitations in building team energy Building effective coordinated team energy can be challenging due to the need to create understanding and consistency among team members.

In terms of reporting, there are the following problems : 1) Insufficient or unsystematic data. Insufficient or unsystematic data collection may prevent planning and decision-making from being realistic. In addition, inaccurate or unreliable data negatively affects correct decision-making. 2) Lack of clarity in goals and indicators. Lack of clarity in goals and indicators may lead to inadequate reporting in evaluating the success of a project or learning activity. 3) Unsystematic or informal reporting may prevent data from being appropriately used for decision-making or planning. 4) Lack of understanding of data use. Lack of understanding of data use may prevent reporting from being fully used for decision-making or planning.

Budgetary aspects There are problems as follows: 1) 1) Lack or insufficiency of budget can prevent learning promotion activities from being fully implemented, or may cause some activities that could be effective to be reduced or discontinued. 2) Insufficient budget allocation cannot fully support the needs of potential learning activities or projects. 3) Limitations in identifying or being able to plan budget use can cause disorderly and inappropriate distribution of funds. 4) Limitations in access to resources. Lack of necessary resources can prevent the proper purchase of equipment or facilities necessary for learning promotion.

2. The quantitative research results of the 111 respondents, the majority were male, 78 people (70.30%), aged between 35 and 44 years, and between 45 and 54 years (30.30%), and had a bachelor's degree (66.70%). and the results of the study on the level of museum management problems in promoting learning for people in the upper northeastern region 1 as shown in Table 1

Table 1. Level of museum management problems in promoting learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1

Museum Management	Problem level			number
	\bar{X}	SD	Interpretation	
1. Planning	3.82	0.53	a lot	1
2. Organization	3.77	0.64	a lot	2
3. Human resource management	3.60	0.56	a lot	6
4. Management	3.53	0.66	a lot	7
5. Coordination	3.63	0.70	a lot	5
6. Reporting	3.73	0.58	a lot	3
7. Budget	3.70	0.68	a lot	4
together	3.68	0.62	a lot	

From the table, it was found that the overall problems of museum management in promoting learning of people in the upper northeastern region 1 were at a high level (\bar{x} = 3.68, SD = 0.62). When considering each aspect, it was found that, number 1, planning (\bar{x} = 3.82, SD = 0.54), number 2, organization (\bar{x} = 3.77, SD = 0.64), number 3, reporting (\bar{x} = 3.73, SD = 0.58), number 4, budget (\bar{x} = 3.70, SD = 0.68), number 5, coordination (\bar{x} = 3.63, SD = 0.70), number 6, personnel management (\bar{x} = 3.60, SD = 0.56), and number 7, management (\bar{x} = 3.537, SD = 0.66), respectively.

Phase 2 To create the strategy for developing museum management to promote learning for people in the upper northeastern region 1. consists of 4 strategies including Development Strategy 1: Developing human resources to properly develop museums in terms of planning. Strategy 2: Develop the museum in terms of organization. Development Strategy 3: Implementing the development of museums to produce accurate reports. Development Strategy 4: Developing museums in managing budgets effectively and Evaluation results of the draft strategy for the development of museum management to promote learning for people in the upper northeastern region of the 30 respondents, the majority were male (7.00 %) and were aged between 45 and 54 years (6.34 %). 60.00 percent have a master's degree and are married. 76.67 percent, and the results of the evaluation of the strategy for developing museum management to promote learning for people in the upper northeastern region 1. It was found that the mean and standard deviation of the suitability and feasibility of the strategy were found to be at the highest level of suitability overall. As for the feasibility of the strategy It is at a high level when considering each strategic issue. at a high level.

VI. DISCUSSION

The researcher brought the findings for discussion. Details are as follows:

1. Results of the study on The Problems in museum management in promoting learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1. , it was found that the overall problems of museum management in promoting learning of people in the upper northeastern region 1 were at a high level number 1, planning, number 2, organization, number 3, reporting, number 4, budget, number 5, coordination, number 6, personnel management number 7, management respectively, are consistent with the POSDCoRB management process concept. By Luther Gulick and Lyndall Urwick It consists of 7 steps: Planning , Organization , Staffing , Directing , Coordination , Reporting , and Budgeting , which are the foundations of organizational management. Other important management functions include Leading and Controlling (Charoenphol Suwannachote, 2008).

2. Results of the strategy determination for museum management development to promote learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1 consist of 4 strategies as follows: Strategy 1 : Developing human resources to properly implement museum planning development. Strategy 2: Develop the museum in terms of organization. Strategy 3: Developing museums to produce accurate reports ; and Strategy 4: Developing museums to manage their budgets effectively. Consistent with the research on the promotion of museum tourism in Thailand with the concept of destination museums, the research results found that museum development activities should be organized by organizing exhibitions in the museum, technological innovation, museum tourism activities, facilities and services in the museum, management of logistics and transportation systems , souvenir shops, tour guides or interpreters, and accommodation businesses around the museum to be a part of stimulating tourism in the museum. In addition, personnel should be developed to interact and work together between stakeholders from both the museum and tourism sides to create a museum tourism network. (Tha Pakorn Thongkammuch , Kesawadee Phutthaphumphithak and Orrawan Sirisawat Aphichakul , 2021)

The researcher created a strategic model for the development of museum management to promote learning among people in the upper northeastern region as follows:

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Figure 1. Model of the strategy for developing museum management to promote learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1

The model of the strategy for developing museum management to promote learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1 consists of 4 strategies including Strategy 1: Developing human resources to properly carry out museum development in terms of planning. Strategy 2: Develop the museum in terms of organization. Strategy 3: Developing museums to produce accurate reports; and Strategy 4: Developing museums to manage their budgets effectively.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the current study, the author recommends the following measures, as presented below:

Recommendation for applying the research results

1. Policy and systematic proposals for applying the research results the research results on the strategy for developing museum management to promote learning among people in the upper northeastern region 1 can be used to determine policies and improve the museum management system as follows:

1.1. Policy proposals

1.1.1 Determining the strategy for developing museums support the development of personnel to have knowledge and skills in museum management planning by organizing training and promoting learning through the development of specialized courses, creating policies to support local museums to receive sufficient budgets and resources to create management efficiency.

1.1.2 Promoting cooperation between the public and private sectors promote the establishment of cooperation networks between museums at the local, national and international levels, based on the guidelines of the international Council of Museums (ICOM)** to create operational standards.

1.1.3 Setting clear goals for each strategy. setting measurable goals for each strategy, such as increasing the number of personnel trained in planning or increasing the rate of efficient use of financial resources.

1.2. The systemic proposals

1.2.1 Developing a management system, create a museum management system that is consistent with the strategy, such as a work planning system that emphasizes the participation process from the community and local personnel, and develop a reporting and evaluation system** that can link data with relevant agencies, such as the Ministry of Culture or tourism organizations.

1.2.2 Use of technology, develop a digital system for exhibition management, budget management, and reporting by introducing technology to help increase operational efficiency, and create an application or online platform that links museums in the upper northeastern region 1 to promote learning and access to information for the public.

1.2.3 Establish a museum management committee, establish a museum management committee in each area, emphasizing cooperation from the public, private, and community sectors to ensure sustainable management.

1.2.4 Promote knowledge and research, establish a learning center or specialized research unit to support studies on museum development and the application of research results to the context of the area.

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Citation: Kritsada Chaopron, Bussagorn Suksan and Krittikar Sanposh. (2024). Strategy for Developing Museum Management to Promote Learning for the People of The Upper Northeastern Region 1. International Journal of Management, 15(6), 109–119.

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